

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON *SAMPRAPTI* OF HYPERTENSION THROUGH AYURVEDA

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension, a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, is increasingly prevalent globally. In Ayurvedic Science, there is no description of such a single disease that can similar to hypertension. But in Ayurveda, it is stated that one should not be ashamed of one's inability to name a disease since all disorders cannot be given standard names. Such a Diseases should be understood and treated considering their nature, pathogenesis, location, and etiology. This article explores the understanding of *samprapti* of hypertension through ayurvedic prospective, highlighting the role of *Tridoshas*, *Manas*, and the concept of *Shadkriyakal* (Six stages of Pathogenesis), *Avarana* (occlusion) in its pathogenesis. This comprehensive review aims to provide a framework to understand *samprapti* of hypertension through ayurvedic prospective.

KEYWORDS: Hypertension, Pathogenesis, *Samprapti*, *Shadkriyakala*, *Avarana*, *Dosha*.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is the science that gives the important keys to basic happy and healthy life. After birth human being goes through many stages of life. These stages are concerned with the

Bala of Sharira and prone to particular *Dosha* and particular diseases. Thus, aging is one of the most important factors which can afflict the healthy stage of the human being. The second is a hereditary factor that also can afflict the healthy internal environment of the human being. The disease Hypertension is neither denoted in *Granthas*, but in Ayurveda, such diseases should be understood and treated according to the disease's nature and its pathogenesis, location, and etiological factors.^[1]

HTN is also known as a 'silent killer. The majority of 'patients' with hypertension are unaware of the problem due to its unwarming signs or symptoms.^[2] Based on causative factors it's classified as Primary & Secondary hypertension. Many factors and conditions may play a part in the progression of HTN like as smoking, overweight or obesity, physical inactivity, excessive salt intake, alcohol consumption, stress, and family history of high blood pressure.^[3] Among the persons identified as being hypertensive, only half are being treated and out of those receiving treatment, only half have their blood pressure normal. Along with all these problems the lifelong and palliative treatment of hypertension in modern science induces many side effects. Therefore, to attain and maintain good health, hypertensive patients are looking towards Ayurveda.

Nidana's for Hypertension in Ayurveda

According to Ayurveda, primary hypertension is caused by an imbalance in the three *doshas* - *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha* - which are influenced by genetic and environmental factors. Based on physiological components of *Dosha*, *Dushya* and *Srotas*, etc. involved in regulating the normal blood pressure, it is evident that indulgence in the *Nidana* or causative factors responsible for the vitiation of these factors will cause *Dosha-Dhatu Dushti* and in form of its after effect, the *Samprapti* of the disease hypertension gets triggered. So, *Nidana* responsible mainly for *Vata Dushti*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*, and *Rakta Dushti*, and the *Dushti* of their respective *Srotas*, should be considered as causative factors either individually or collectively. *Nidana* which affects the *Manas* should be considered in particular as *Manas* also plays a very important role in the pathology of hypertension.^[4]

Samprapti of Hypertension in Ayurveda

A] Probable *Samprapti* of Hypertension in Ayurveda as per *Shadakriyakala*

The pathogenesis of hypertension takes place at both the physical and psychic levels one at a time or simultaneously depending upon the *Dosha Dushya Sannimurchhana*. Mild to moderate hypertension in most cases does not exhibit any symptoms. But some patients have symptoms

like Giddiness, Headache, Chest pain, Palpitation, etc. In the different stages of a disease, *Prasaravastha* is the stage where the *Doshas* move out from their respective sites and along with *Rakta* circulate all over the body, causing certain mild, nonspecific symptoms. This in turn hampers the functions of the respective *Srotas* in the beginning and later they bring about structural changes as well, leading to *Kha-Vaigunya*. Then, these *Doshas* get lodged at susceptible sites of *Kha-Vaigunya* which in this case can be: the heart, brain, kidneys, eyes, and blood vessels. It is at this stage that the actual *Sthana Samshraya* and *Vyakta Avastha* (manifestation of specific symptoms) occurs, causing diseases of these vital organs. Later, in the *Bheda avastha* (complicated stage), there occurs severe damage to these organs, making the disease *Asadhya* (incurable) and sometimes leading to death itself. Thus, hypertension can be taken as a sub-clinical condition where the disease process is still in progress making it a risk factor for more dangerous diseases of the heart, brain, kidneys, eyes, etc. according to Ayurveda.^[5]

B] *Samprapti* of Hypertension in Ayurveda as per modern view

The various factors (*Aaharaj*, *Viharaja*, and *Manasika Nidanas*) interact with each other and influence the pathogenesis of this condition. The main determinants of blood pressure are cardiac output and peripheral resistance. Increase in blood pressure, there should be an increase in either cardiac output or peripheral resistance. It is due to the influence of risk factors that one or more of the different regulatory mechanisms of blood pressure gets hampered causing the blood pressure to increase. Defects in renal homeostasis cause increased salt and water retention (*Kleda*). This increases the plasma and extracellular fluid

thus increasing the cardiac output. This is one mechanism that leads to increased Blood pressure. The other mechanism is a defect in hormonal regulation of Blood pressure (Renin-angiotensin mechanism) that causes vasoconstriction which leads to increased peripheral resistance. This may be understood as the pathology due to *Dooshana* (vitiating) of *Rakta* and *Pitta* due to Excessive spicy food intake, Smoking, Alcohol, Tea, etc. As *Pitta Dushti* due to endocrinal defects. Impaired autonomic nervous system functioning causing the rise in blood pressure may be seen as *Dushti* of *Vata*. Sushruta has mentioned that *Vata Dooshita Rakta* (blood vitiating by Vata) is both *Sheeghra Gami* (fast moving) and *Askandi* (hemodilution). Both these factors lead to changes in peripheral resistance. Hemodilution increases cardiac output and *Vata* being *Ruksha* (dry) and *Sheeta* (cold) in nature may cause stiffness of vessels which increases peripheral vascular resistance and leads to hypertension. The second mechanism is due to defects in the vascular smooth muscles (atherosclerotic changes caused by factors like hyperlipidemia, Obesity) where the blood vessels lose their normal tone and this increases peripheral resistance, thus causing hypertension. This pathology may be due to the vitiating of *Kapha Dosha* and *Medo Dhatu* because of excessive sweet items, non-veg, fatty foods intake, and Physical inactivity. The third mechanism due to the involvement of *Manasika* factors like *Atichinta*, *Bhaya*, *Krodha*, and physical inactivity does *Tridosha Prakopa* with *Rajas* and *Tamas Prakopa* which developed stress or anxiety causes disturbed in sleep and appetite further its responsible for impairment in physiological homeostasis which increases heart rate and vasoconstriction thus increasing the cardiac output and peripheral resistance that leads to increased Blood pressure Based on these points it can be concluded that the pathology of hypertension involves one or all the three *Doshas* and *Manasika* factors which in turn affect to cause of this condition.^[6]

C] *Samprapti* as per *Aavarana* concept

As blood circulation is mainly the function of *Vata*, its impairment is certain in Hypertension. It may be impaired by its *Prakopa* due to *Vataja Nidanas* or may get vitiated by the influence of other *Doshas* and *Dhatu*s. This is where the concept of occlusion of the normal functioning of *Vata* plays a major role in the pathogenesis of hypertension. The normal course of *Vata* can be occluded by *Pitta*, *Kapha*, *Rakta*, and or *Medas*. These *Anya Dosha Avarana* pathologies can be considered under hypertension due to increased hormonal and enzyme action,^[7] decreased sodium excretion,^[8] change in the chemical constituents in the blood, and atherosclerotic changes in the arteries due to lipid deposition.^[9] Another type of occlusive pathology happens when there is *Anyonya Avarana* of *Vata* (mutual occlusion between subtypes of *Vata*). The subtypes of *Vata* such as *Prana* and *Vyana Vata* obstruct each other and cause the disease. This condition can be considered hypertension due to the hampered autonomic nervous system as it plays an important role in the regulation of blood pressure.^[10] Charaka and Sushruta have enumerated and explained many different types of mutual occlusions of *Dosha* and occlusion of one *Dosha* by other *Dosha* or *Dhatu* and in many of these conditions; symptoms of hypertension such as giddiness, headache, and fatigue have been mentioned. These conditions are: *Pittavritavata*, *Vyanavrita Prana*, *Pittavrita Prana*, *Pittavrita Vyana*, *Pittavrita Samana* and *Pittavrita Udana*. Other conditions where these symptoms are seen together are *Amashayagata Vata*.

Rakta Dushti & *Pradoshaja Vikara* and *Pittaja Hridroga*. *Vyana Vata* is said to be responsible for *Sweda* (sweat) and *Asruk Sravana* (ejection of blood) and if it gets vitiated it produces diseases that will affect the entire body. This can be correlated to hypertension as excessive perspiration is a symptom of hypertension.^[11]

SAMPRAPTI GHATAK: Pathological factors

Sr No	<i>Samprapti Ghatak</i> of Hypertension.		
1	<i>Sharirika Dosha</i>	<i>Vata</i>	<i>Vyana, Prana, Samana, Apana, Udana</i>
		<i>Pitta</i>	<i>Pachaka, Sadhaka, Ranjaka</i>
		<i>Kapha</i>	<i>Avalambak</i>
2	<i>Manasika Dosha</i>	<i>Rajasa, Tamasa</i>	
3	<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda</i>	
4	<i>Agni</i>	<i>Jathargni, Dhatwagni Mandya</i>	
5	<i>Aama</i>	<i>Sama</i>	
6	<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Manovaha</i>	
7	<i>Srotodusti</i>	<i>Atipravriti, Sanga, Vimarga-gamana</i>	
8	<i>Adhistana</i>	<i>Hrudaya, Dhamani</i>	
9	<i>Udbhavastana</i>	<i>Aamashaya, Pakwashaya</i>	

10	<i>Rogamarga</i>	<i>Madhyma, Bahya</i>
11	<i>Vyaktasthana</i>	<i>Sarvadaihika</i>
12	<i>Sadhyasadhyta</i>	<i>Kruchhasadhya</i>
13	<i>Swarupa</i>	<i>Chirkari</i>

CONCLUSION

This comprehensive review provides way to understand pathological concepts of hypertension as per ayurveda and helpful to make strategy of ayurvedic treatment plan of hypertension.

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